

STUDIES ON ADSORPTION IN RELATION TO CONSTITUTION, PART II. ADSORPTION OF ORGANIC ACIDS ON ACTIVATED SILICA GEL

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Relationship between constitution and adsorption on active silica gel in the case of a large number of organic acids and the effect of substitution of polar groups on adsorption have been investigated.

Attempts have often been made to correlate the constitution of molecules with their adsorption on different surfaces. As early as 1896 Walker and Appleyard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 1334) observed that the adsorption of acids on silk depended upon their chemical nature. Aromatic acids gave an adsorption of 23%, the adsorption of fatty acids was 6%, whilst the mineral acids occupied a mean position with an adsorption of 11-16%. Fromageot and Wurmser (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, 179, 972) studied the adsorption of organic acids from aqueous solutions on charcoal and found that the amount of adsorption increased in an irregular manner with the number of carboxyl groups in the molecule. Schilow and Nekrassow (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 65) found that the adsorption of fatty monobasic and saturated dibasic acids on active charcoal always increased with the number of carbon atoms in the molecule. They further found that the successive differences between members of the homologous series attained a maximum at the fifth or sixth member. Landt and Knop (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, 162, 331) observed that aqueous solutions of monobasic acids displaced hydrochloric acid molecules adsorbed on charcoal in direct proportion to the number of carbon atoms contained in the molecule. Apart from the influence of the number of carbon atoms, the effect of introduction in the molecule of various active groups like -OH, -SO₃H, -COOH, =CO, -CN, -Cl, double bond etc., on adsorption has been investigated by various workers. Schilow and Nekrassow observed that the introduction of double bonds and other active groups always led to increased adsorption whilst the introduction of hydroxyl and sulphonic acid groups produced a diminished adsorption. The result with regard to hydroxyl group was corroborated by Linner and Gortner (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 35) but contrary to Schilow and Nekrassow, they found a decrease with double bonds.

The adsorption of aromatic acids has generally been found to be higher than that for aliphatic acids (Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", 1926, p. 197). Thus, Ockrent (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 613) found that aqueous solutions of benzoic, salicylic, and toluic acids show a much stronger adsorption than corresponding solutions of monochloroacetic, formic, and trichloroacetic acids, on active charcoal. This is also borne out by the experiments of Schilow and Nekrassow who found the adsorption of monochloroacetic acid to be 25%, whilst on the substitution of Cl by a phenyl group, the resulting phenylacetic acid gave an adsorption of 62.4%. Jain and Jha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 685) have found the adsorption of dibasic acids to increase with the higher members of the homologous series. They have, however, found a lower adsorption for phthalic acids.

As has been pointed out by Freundlich and Heller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2228) a factor of great importance in adsorption is the solvent. Thus, Jermolenko and Ginsberg (*Kolloid Shurn.*, 1939, 8, 263) found that chloroacetic acids from aqueous solutions were adsorbed on charcoal in the order: mono > di > tri, whilst in benzene or alcohol, the adsorption was exactly in the reverse order (*cf.* Sata and Kurano, *Kolloid Z.*, 1932, 60, 137). That adsorption depends upon the nature of the solvent is also shown by the work of Bhatnagar, Kapur, and Bhatnagar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 361). These authors found that the adsorption from

aqueous solutions of aliphatic acids by acid-condensed phenolic resins increased with increasing molecular weight, but the behaviour was reversed in the case of non-polar solvents. Adsorption by amino- and protein-resins was found to increase on the introduction of polar groups in the acid molecule. Thus, even with the same adsorbent, a comparison of adsorbability can only be permissible when the solvent is also the same (*cf.* also Cook, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 633; Zechmeister and Jorgens, *Naturwiss.*, 26, 495; Elder and Springer, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, 44, 943).

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 453), the adsorption of alkaloids from alcoholic solutions on active silica gel was measured. It was found that molecules with similar structure have similar adsorption. With a view to further studying the relationship between constitution and adsorption on active silica gel, the adsorption of a large number of organic acids, and the effect of substitution of polar groups on adsorption, have been investigated in the present paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The adsorbent used in these experiments was activated silica gel. The gel was prepared in the laboratory according to Patricks' method from sodium silicate solutions and hydrochloric acid, and obtained in a perfectly transparent, granular form. The gel was washed with repeated changes of hot distilled water, till the washings were neutral and entirely free from chlorides. The gel was activated as described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*).

Alcoholic solutions (75 c.c.) of different acids were treated in stoppered bottles with 10g. of the activated gel in each case. The amount of adsorption was determined by titration against *N*/100 solution of caustic potash before and after adsorption. A mixture of neutral red and methylene blue was used as the indicator. The bottles were occasionally shaken and left for 72 hours to attain equilibrium. The acid solutions used in these experiments are all *M*/100 in concentration, except where otherwise stated. The temperature was throughout 25°. The experimental results are recorded in Tables I to VI.

TABLE I

Adsorption of monobasic acids from alcoholic solutions on silica gel

Acids.	Formula.	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount ad- sorbed.	% Adsorp- tion.	No. of atoms in molecule.
Formic ...	HCOOH	10.0	0.8	9.2	92.0	1
Acetic ...	CH ₃ COOH	10.0	4.0	6.0	60.0	2
Propionic ...	C ₂ H ₅ COOH	11.2	5.0	6.2	55.4	3
Butyric ...	C ₃ H ₇ COOH	10.8	5.1	5.7	52.8	4
Valeric ...	C ₄ H ₉ COOH	11.2	5.0	6.2	55.4	5
Caproic ...	C ₅ H ₁₁ COOH	11.2	5.1	6.1	55.3	6
Pelargonic ...	C ₈ H ₁₇ COOH	11.2	5.0	6.2	55.4	9
Undecylic ...	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ COOH	9.8	4.2	5.6	57.1	11
Lauric ...	C ₁₁ H ₂₃ COOH	10.0	4.1	5.9	59.0	12
Myristic ...	C ₁₃ H ₂₇ COOH	10.0	4.1	5.9	59.0	14
Palmitic ...	C ₁₅ H ₃₁ COOH	10.0	4.1	5.9	59.0	16
Margaric ...	C ₁₇ H ₃₅ COOH	9.8	4.1	5.7	58.2	17
Stearic ...	C ₁₇ H ₃₅ COOH	10.0	4.3	5.7	57.0	18

TABLE II

Adsorption of dibasic acids from alcoholic solutions on silica gel

Acids.	Formula.	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount ad- sorbed.	% Adsorp- tion.	No. of atoms in molecule.
Oxalic ...	COOH·COOH	21.6	3.6	18.0	83.3	2
Malonic ...	CH ₂ (COOH) ₂	20.0	3.8	16.2	81.0	3
Succinic ...	C ₂ H ₄ (COOH) ₂	20.6	8.2	12.4	60.2	4
Glutaric ...	C ₃ H ₆ (COOH) ₂	21.6	11.4	10.2	47.2	5
Adipic ...	C ₄ H ₈ (COOH) ₂	22.6	13.2	9.4	41.6	6
Phthalic ...	C ₆ H ₄ (COOH) ₂	22.2	6.2	16.0	72.1	8

TABLE III

Effect of substitution by hydroxyl groups on adsorption

Acid.	Formula.	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	% Adsorption.	Dif.
Propionic	... C ₃ H ₇ COOH	11'2 5'0	6'2	55'3	0'0	
Lactic	.. C ₃ H ₅ (OH).COOH	10'6 2'8	7'8	73'6	28'3	
Succinic	.. C ₄ H ₆ (COOH) ₂	20'6 8'2	12'4	60'2	0'0	
Malic	... C ₃ H ₅ (OH)(COOH) ₂	21'2 7'6	13'6	64'2	4'0	
r-Tartaric	... C ₂ H ₄ (OH) ₂ (COOH) ₂	20'8 6'8	14'0	67'3	7'1	
Benzoic	.. C ₆ H ₅ COOH	11'0 5'6	5'4	49'1	0'0	
m-Hydroxybenzoic	... (OH)C ₆ H ₄ COOH	10'4 4'6	5'8	55'8	6'7	
Salicylic	... (OH)C ₆ H ₄ COOH	11'4 3'4	8'0	70'0	20'9	
Naphthoic	... C ₁₀ H ₇ COOH	11'0 4'2	6'8	61'8	0'0	
2(OH)Naphthoic	... C ₁₀ H ₆ (OH) ₂ COOH	10'8 1'4	9'4	87'0	25'2	
Phenylacetic	... C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ COOH	11'0 4'4	6'6	60'0	0'0	
Mandelic	... C ₆ H ₅ CH(OH)COOH	11'2 1'3	9'9	90'2	30'1	

TABLE IV

Effect of substitution of different groups in acetic acid

Acids.	Formula.	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	% Adsorption.	Dif.
Acetic	... CH ₃ COOH	10'0 4'0	6'0	60'0	0'0	
Monochloroacetic	CH ₂ ClCOOH	10'2 2'0	8'2	80'4	20'4	
Dichloroacetic	CHCl ₂ COOH	10'2 0'9	9'3	91'2	31'2	
Trichloroacetic	CCl ₃ COOH	10'4 0'2	10'2	98'1	38'1	
Trifluoroacetic	CF ₃ COOH	10'2 0'0	10'2	100'0	40'0	
Phenylacetic	... C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ COOH	11'0 4'4	6'6	60'0	0'0	
Malonic	... COOH.CH ₂ COOH	20'0 3'8	16'2	82'0	21'0	
Mandelic	... C ₆ H ₅ CH(OH)COOH	11'2 1'3	9'9	90'1	30'1	
Propiolic	... CH≡C COOH	10'6 0'8	9'8	92'5	32'5	
Propionic	... CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH	11'2 5'0	6'2	55'3	-4'7	

TABLE V

Effect of substitution of different groups in benzoic and succinic acids

A. Benzoic						B. Succinic							
Acid.	Formula.	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	% Adsorption	Dif.	Acid.	Formula.	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	% Adsorption.	Dif.
Benzoic	C ₆ H ₅ COOH	11'0 5'6	5'4	49'1	0'0		Succinic	C ₂ H ₄ (COOH) ₂	20'6 8'2	12'4	60'2	0'0	
o-Chlorobenzoic	C ₆ H ₄ Cl COOH	8'9 2'6	6'3	70'8	21'7		Dibromosuccinic	C ₂ H ₂ Br ₂ (COOH) ₂	21'0 10'0	11'0	52'4	-7'8	
p-Chlorobenzoic	C ₆ H ₄ Cl COOH	9'0 2'9	6'1	67'7	18'6		Malic	C ₃ H ₅ (OH)(COOH) ₂	21'2 7'6	13'6	64'2	4'0	
o-Bromobenzoic	C ₆ H ₄ Br COOH	10'8 3'0	7'8	72'2	23'1		r-Tartaric	C ₂ H ₄ (OH) ₂ (COOH) ₂	20'8 6'8	14'0	67'3	7'1	
m-Bromobenzoic	C ₆ H ₄ Br COOH	10'8 3'0	7'8	72'2	23'1		l-Tartaric	C ₂ H ₄ (OH) ₂ (COOH) ₂	20'8 6'6	14'2	68'3	8'1	
o-Nitrobenzoic	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ COOH	10'2 2'2	8'0	78'4	29'3		Meso-tartaric	C ₂ H ₄ (OH) ₂ (COOH) ₂	21'0 6'4	14'6	69'5	9'3	
p-Nitrobenzoic	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ COOH	10'4 2'8	7'6	73'1	24'0		Phthalic	C ₆ H ₄ (COOH) ₂	22'2 6'2	16'0	72'1	11'9	
m-Nitrobenzoic	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ COOH	10'2 2'4	7'8	76'5	27'4								
o-Tolnic	CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	10'2 5'6	4'6	45'1	-4'0								
m-Tolnic	CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	10'2 5'6	4'6	45'1	-4'0								
p-Tolnic	CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	10'6 5'0	5'6	52'8	3'7								
o-Hydroxybenzoic	(OH)C ₆ H ₄ COOH	11'4 3'4	8'0	70'0	20'9								
m-Hydroxybenzoic	(OH)C ₆ H ₄ COOH	10'4 4'6	5'8	55'8	6'7								
Anthranilic	NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	11'0 2'6	8'4	76'4	27'3								

DISCUSSION

The adsorptions of organic compounds from aqueous solutions on active charcoal, have often been examined in relation to Traube's rule. Traube showed that with successive members in a homologous series, the concentrations have to be diminished about threefold, in order that the same lowering of surface tension may be produced with each addition of a CH_2 group. As the lowering of surface tension is intimately connected with adsorption, Traube's rule has been stated by Freundlich to denote that the adsorption of organic substances from aqueous solutions increases regularly as one ascends the homologous series (Freundlich, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 67, 385; "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", 1926, p. 195). Freundlich verified the rule in the case of the first four members of the fatty acid series. Subsequent investigators have generally supported Freundlich's conclusions, though occasional divergences have been noticed. Thus Fromageot and Wurmser (*loc. cit.*) record an irregularity in adsorption with successive members of the fatty acid series. Schilow and Nekrassow (*loc. cit.*) observed that the increase in adsorption with the addition of each CH_2 group, attained a maximum value between the fifth and sixth member of the fatty acid series. Previous work had mostly been limited to the first four members of the fatty acids. Linner and Gortner (*loc. cit.*) have more recently examined the adsorption of a larger number of the fatty acid homologues and found that Traube's rule is followed better in the case of more dilute solutions.

In the present experiments the adsorption of 13 members of the fatty acid homologues by silica gel from alcoholic solutions, have been measured. The results are recorded in Table I. An examination of the data shows that formic acid gives an abnormally large adsorption of 92%. The other members of the homologous series from acetic acid to stearic acid, all give adsorptions which lie between 52.8 and 60%. It is thus remarkable that as the number of carbon atoms in the molecule increases from 2 to 18, the percentage adsorption varies but slightly and may be considered to be roughly constant. This result is thus quite different from the adsorption on the surface of carbon, where adsorption increases with each successive member in accordance with Traube's rule. Traube's rule, however, has generally been applied to the case of aqueous solutions. As the change in surface tension in the case organic solvents is generally small (*cf.* Gilbert, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 543). Traube's rule will not necessarily apply to adsorption from organic solvents. In the case of silica gel, however, considerable adsorptions have been observed from benzene, toluene, nitrobenzene and other organic solvents (Patrick and Jones, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1). It is evident that in the case of organic solvents, the lowering of surface tension cannot be considered as the chief criterion of adsorbability and consequently Traube's rule will not apply.

In the case of adsorption by silica gel, the reverse of the effect required by Traube's rule has been observed by several investigators. Holmes and McKelvey found a reversal of Traube's rule in the case of the adsorption of fatty acids from toluene solutions (*ibid.*, 1928, 32, 1522). Bartell and Fu (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 676) investigated the adsorption by silica gel both from aqueous and from carbon tetrachloride solutions. The adsorption from aqueous solutions was very slight. In the case of CCl_4 solutions, they found a similar reversal of Traube's rule: the adsorption of the first four members of the fatty acids, decreased as one ascended the series. Apart from this reversal effect, if one compares the results of Bartell and Fu with the observations of Freundlich on adsorption from aqueous solutions by blood charcoal, one finds that the values of a_{n+1}/a_n , the ratio between the adsorption of successive members, is generally much higher in the case of charcoal than in the case of silica gel. In the following table, some of the data for the two adsorbents with different solvents, are given for comparison.

TABLE VI

Acids.	Adsorption on blood charcoal from aqueous solutions (Freundlich).		Adsorption on silica gel from CCl_4 solutions (Bartell and Fu).			
	Conc.	a_{n+1}/a_n	Conc.	a_{n+1}/a_n	Conc.	C_{n+1}/a_n
Formic	... 0'10N	—	0'10N	—	0'02N	—
Acetic	... 0'10	1'26	0'10	0'836	0'02	0'879
Propionic	... 0'10	1'55	0'10	0'879	0'02	0'911
Butyric	... 0'10	1'36	0'10	0'904	0'02	0'929

As is clearly seen from the above table, in the case of adsorption from aqueous solutions on charcoal, the increase between successive members is about 55%, whilst in the case of CCl_4 solutions on silica gel, there is a mean decrease which is only about 12%, the solution in both the cases being $M/10$. With a more dilute CCl_4 solution, $M/50$, the difference in the adsorption of successive members is further reduced to 9'4%. From Bartell and Fu's data, it thus appears, that in dilute solutions the adsorption by silica gel from organic solvents, tends to become more or less comparable from member to member in the homologous series. This is in accordance with the observations recorded in the present experiments, with alcoholic solutions. It would be relevant to mention that in the case of aqueous solutions the adsorptions of successive members persist in showing a very marked increase even at a concentration of $M/100$ (*cf.* Schilow and Nekrassow *loc. cit.*).

So far as the present experiments go, it might be considered that the adsorption of the fatty acid homologues on silica gel is independent of the length of the carbon chain (see Table I). This result can be explained if we consider that the adsorbed molecules are definitely oriented. The structure may be considered akin to that given by Langmuir for fatty acid films on water (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 1848). The carboxyl group, which is the active group of the fatty acid molecule, will be directed towards the surface of the adsorbent and the saturated CH_2 group will form the outermost layer. The adsorbed molecules will thus be more or less with their lengths at right angles to the surface. Such an oriented structure will give the same adsorption for all members of the fatty acid series irrespective of the length of the carbon chain. The amount of adsorption in every case will depend upon the area covered by the carboxyl group and the area in the case of all monobasic fatty acids will be the same. Although the above represents the structure of the adsorbed layer in a general way, a certain distortion in the orientation will set in owing to the presence of a polar group in the solvent itself.

TABLE VII

Acid.	Formula.	$M/20$ soln.				$M/10$ soln.*			
		C_1	C_2	a	%ads.	C_1	C_2	a	%ads.
Oxalic	$(\text{COOH})_2$	9'6	6'1	3'5	30'2	20'4	16'2	4'2	25'9
Malonic	$\text{CH}_2(\text{COOH})_2$	9'6	8'6	1'0	10'6	20'0	18'8	1'2	6'0
Succinic	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{COOH})_2$	9'7	8'6	0'6	6'2	20'6	19'8	0'8	3'9
Glutaric	$\text{C}_3\text{H}_6(\text{COOH})_2$	9'7	9'1	0'6	6'2	20'6	19'8	0'8	3'9
Adipic	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_8(\text{COOH})_2$	9'7	9'1	0'6	6'2	20'8	20'0	0'8	3'9
Phthalic	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{COOH})_2$	9'7	9'1	0'8	8'2	21'0	20'0	1'0	4'8

* 10 c.c. solution titrated against $N/10$ -KOH.

Variation of Adsorption of Dibasic Acids with Concentration

In Table II, the adsorptions of dibasic acids on silica gel are recorded. It will be seen that the percentage adsorption in this series shows a regular decrease with increase in number of carbon atoms in the chain. The adsorptions of dibasic acids on active charcoal from aqueous solutions have been measured by several authors. Fromageot and Wurmser (*loc. cit.*) did not find any difference for oxalic and succinic acids. Schilow and Nekrassow (*loc. cit.*) on the other hand, found an increase in adsorption as the number of carbon atoms in the molecule increased. This was confirmed by Linner and Gortner (*loc. cit.*) for concentrations below 0.05M, but the values approached each other in the vicinity of this concentration, except for oxalic acid. The present results are thus the complete reversal of the above observations. If we multiply the adsorption coefficients by the number of carbon atoms contained in the molecule, we get the figures as shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Acid.	Adsorption coeff.	No. of carbon atoms.	Product.
Oxalic acid	83.3	2	166.6
Malonic acid	81.0	3	243.0
Succinic acid	60.2	4	240.8
Glutaric acid	47.2	5	236.0
Adipic acid	41.6	6	249.6

TABLE IX

Acid.	% Adsorption.	Dissociation constant.
Acetic	60.0	1.8×10^{-5}
Monochloroacetic	80.4	1.56×10^{-3}
Dichloroacetic	91.2	5.1×10^{-2}
Trichloroacetic	98.1	3.0×10^{-1}

Thus, (Table VIII) excluding the single case of oxalic acid, the product is a constant within 3% of the mean value, 242.4. This strongly suggests that the orientation of the adsorbed molecules is such that they lie flat on the surface of the adsorbent. In other words, both the carboxyl groups now lie on the surface, and as one ascends the homologous series, the introduction of a CH₂ group increases the distance between the two carboxyls. Thus with the increase in the number of carbon atoms in the molecule, the area of the surface covered by the molecule also increases proportionately. The percentage adsorption thus decreases in a regular manner with increase in the number of carbon atoms.

Changes in the orientation of adsorbed molecules with increasing concentrations have been observed in a few cases. Thus, from the measurement of surface potentials due to phenols adsorbed on the water-air interface (Adam, "Physics and Chemistry of Surface", 1938, p. 137) it has been concluded that as the space available for each molecule on the surface is decreased, it tends to take up an increasingly vertical position, whereas originally it was lying almost flat. The effect of concentration has also been noted by Linner and Gortner (*loc. cit.*). Thus in the present case it is to be expected that as the concentration of the dibasic acids is increased, there would not be enough space after a certain limit for every molecule to lie flat on the surface, and a vertical orientation with only one carboxyl on the surface may become compulsory. In such a case the structure of the adsorbed molecules will be the same as in the case of the monobasic acid series, and the differences from member to member should vanish. That this is actually the case is evident from Table VII, where the percentage adsorption between successive members of the dibasic acid series becomes comparable.

The effect of substitution of hydroxyl group in the molecule on adsorbability is recorded in Table III. The hydroxyl group always produces an increase in adsorptions, but this increase is not constant in all the cases, being only 4% in the case of malic acid and as much 30.1% in the case of mandelic acid. When another OH group is introduced into malic acid the resulting tartaric acid shows a further increase of 3.1%. The results are exactly the reverse of those of Schilow and Nekrassow (*loc. cit.*). It is further interesting to note that the largest increase in the present case *viz.*, in mandelic acid, corresponds to the largest decrease observed by the above-mentioned authors. In this respect the behaviour with silica gel is thus the reverse of what has been observed with charcoal.

Substitution of halogens in the molecule (Tables IV and V) also always leads to an increased adsorption with the single exception of dibromosuccinic acid. In the acetic acid molecule, adsorption increases as the number of halogens introduced is increased. This is in the same order as the dissociation constants (and hence strength) of the resulting acids, as will be apparent from the above table.

Effect of substitution of different groups and radicals in acetic, benzoic and succinic acid molecules are shown in Tables IV and V respectively. No further remarks are necessary. It may be said in general that introduction of an active group leads to enhanced adsorption. Positional isomers as a rule do not differ much in their adsorbability, as also is the case with the few optical isomers studied.

Further work with different solvents is in progress.

In conclusion we must record our thanks to the Patna University for the grant of a research scholarship to one of us (B.P.G.).

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Received May 19, 1943.